

Synthesis and biological evaluation of 3-(phthalimidomethyl)-4-(5-substituted isoxazoline and pyrazoline) substituted benzanilides

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Abstract : 3-Phthalimidomethylbenzoic acids **2** were prepared by treating *N*-hydroxymethylphthalimide **1** with substituted benzoic acids. The corresponding acid chlorides **3** were condensed with 4-aminoacetophenone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to give 3-phthalimidomethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilides **4**. The substituted benzanilide derivatives **4** were condensed with diverse aromatic aldehydes to afford the compounds **5**. Compounds **5a₁-d₇**, on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate and with hydrazine dihydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate afforded the title compounds **6a₁-d₇** and **7a₁-a₉**, respectively. Compounds **6a₁-d₇** and **7a₁-a₉** were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities and **6a₁** and **7a₁** for anthelmintic and hypoglycemic activities.

Keywords : Phthalimide, isoxazole, pyrazole, antimicrobial activity.

The phthalimide compounds and their derivatives are reported to show diverse biological activities^{1,2}, including anticancer, antitumor promoting agent, immunosuppressant, antiviral, hypoglycemic and antimicrobial activities. The wide range of biological and pharmacological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, antidiabetic and antiinflammatory are associated with pyrazoline³⁻⁶ and isoxazolines⁷. Based on these findings and in continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of substituted phthalimido compounds of biological interest⁸, we report here the synthesis and biological evaluation of phthalimidomethyl derivatives containing pyrazoline and isoxazoline moiety (Scheme 1).

The targeted compound *N*-hydroxymethylphthalimide **1** was prepared by Mannich condensation of phthalimide and formalin as per the reported method⁹. Compound **1** was condensed with various substituted benzoic acids in ethanol to yield **2** which on treatment with thionyl chloride gave corresponding acid chlorides **3**. Compounds **4a-g** were prepared by heating acid chlorides **3** with 4-aminoacetophenone in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃. The condensation of substituted benzanilide derivatives **4** with various arylaldehydes in ethanol afforded 3-phthalimidomethyl-4-substituted cinammoyl substituted benzanilides **5a₁-d₇**, which on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and hydrazine dihydrochloride in the presence

of sodium acetate afforded the title compounds **6a₁-d₇** and **7a₁-a₉**, respectively. Products of the representative compounds (**2a**, **3a**, **4a**, **5a₁**, **6a₁** and **7a₁**) were characterized by elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, NMR, mass).

Results and discussion

The CMC suspension of synthesized compounds were shown to produce reduction in the blood glucose concentration between 8 h of administration in two methods, normoglycemic rats¹⁰ and alloxan induced hyperglycemic rats¹¹ at a tested dose of 250 mg/kg of body weight. When compared with reference gliclazide administered at a dose of 2.5 mg/kg, **6a₁** and **7a₁** compounds exhibited moderate hypoglycemic activity.

The antibacterial and antifungal activity of title compounds were determined by agar cup-plate method^{12,13}. Among the compounds, **6b₁**, **6c₁**, **7a₁**, **7a₂** were found to be the most active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* where as **6a₁** and **7a₁** were found to be moderately active against *C. albicans*. However, other compounds were less active in comparison to ampicillin trihydrate and cotrimoxazole which were taken as standard drug for antibacterial and antifungal activity respectively and the results are given in Table 2.

The anthelmintic activity was evaluated on adult Indian earthworm *Pheretima postuma* due to its anatomical and

Scheme 1

physiological resemblance with the intestinal roundworm of human beings¹⁵⁻¹⁷, by using the method of Mathew *et al.*¹⁸. Compounds were tested at two concentration 50 mg/mL and 100 mg/mL and compounds were kept in 1% gum acacia in normal saline. Compounds **6a₁** and **7a₁** showed moderate activity in comparison with piperazine citrate (15 mg/mL). The results are shown in Table 3.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (cm^{-1}) were recorded on Jasco FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) spectra were recorded on Bruker DPX-300 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm). C, H and N analysis were carried

out on Euro EA (Italy) analyzer. Mass spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Hitachi RMU-6L MS 30 instrument. The physical and analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

3-Phthalimidomethyl substituted benzoic acids 2a : To a solution of 2-acetyloxybenzoic acid (7.20 g, 0.04 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) was added a hot solution of compound **1** (0.04 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) with constant stirring followed by conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) and the mixture was kept under reflux on a water bath for 4 h. On cooling, the separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from acetone, **2a** : yield 79%. m.p. 122 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3045 (C-H stretching), 1776 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$ -acyclic), 1703 ($-\text{COOH}$ stretching), 1606 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1407 (C-N stretching in primary

aromatic ring); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 2.1 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 4.2 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.81 (7H, m, ArH), 12.2 (1H, s, COOH); MS (m/z): 339 (M^+) (Found : C, 63.92; H, 4.01; N, 6.41. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_6$: C, 63.72; H, 3.86; N, 4.13%).

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the compounds prepared

Compd.	R	Ar	Molecular formula	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
4a	2-OCOCH ₃	–	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	134
4b	2-Cl	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	139
4c	4-Cl	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	138
4d	2-Br	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Br	130
4e	4-Br	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Br	132
4f	2-NO ₂	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₆	124
4g	4-OH	–	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	128
5a ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₇	161
5a ₂	2-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	163
5a ₃	4-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	168
5a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Br	163
5a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Br	169
5a ₆	2-NO ₂	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₇	154
5a ₇	4-OH	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	152
5b ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₇	166
5b ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	165
5b ₃	4-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	163
5b ₄	2-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Br	167
5b ₅	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Br	166
5b ₆	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₇	156
5b ₇	4-OH	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	151
5c ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	160
5c ₂	2-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	161
5c ₃	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	163
5c ₄	2-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ Br	161
5c ₅	4-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ Br	164
5c ₆	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₆	152
5c ₇	4-OH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	156
5d ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-Furyl	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₇	168
5d ₂	2-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	164
5d ₃	4-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	166
5d ₄	2-Br	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	169
5d ₅	4-Br	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	160
5d ₆	2-NO ₂	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₇	153
5d ₇	4-OH	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	157
6a ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₇	192
6a ₂	2-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	197
6a ₃	4-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	201
6a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Br	204
6a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Br	204
6a ₆	2-NO ₂	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₇	208
6a ₇	4-OH	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₆	198
6b ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇	192

Table-1 (contd.)

6b ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	201
6b ₃	4-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	202
6b ₄	2-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Br	202
6b ₅	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Br	202
6b ₆	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇	205
6b ₇	4-OH	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₆	199
6c ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₆	192
6c ₂	2-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	197
6c ₃	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	205
6c ₄	2-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ Br	200
6c ₅	4-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ Br	202
6c ₆	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₆	204
6c ₇	4-OH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅	201
6d ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-Furyl	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₇	196
6d ₂	2-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	194
6d ₃	4-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	198
6d ₄	2-Br	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₅ Br	201
6d ₅	4-Br	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₅ Br	207
6d ₆	2-NO ₂	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₇	201
6d ₇	4-OH	2-Furyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₆	203
7a ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅	197
7a ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	202
7a ₃	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	204
7a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ Br	196
7a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ Br	193
7a ₆	4-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃ Br	199
7a ₇	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄ Br	202
7a ₈	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₆	207
7a ₉	4-OH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	198

Compounds **2b-g** were prepared similarly.

3-Phthalimidomethyl substituted benzoyl chloride 3a : A mixture of compound **2a** (13.56 g, 0.04 mol) and thionyl chloride (6 mL) in dry benzene was refluxed on a water bath for 2.5 h under anhydrous condition. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to yield the compounds, **3a** : yield 78%, m.p. 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3203 (C-H stretching), 1768 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$ - acyclic), 1698 ($>\text{C}=\text{CO}$), 1606 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1428 (C-N stretching in primary aromatic ring), 723 (C-Cl); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 2.0 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 4.1 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–8.3 (7H, m, ArH); MS (m/z): 357 (M^+) (Found : C, 60.58; H, 3.81; N, 4.09. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_5\text{Cl}$: C, 60.43; H, 3.38; N, 3.92%).

Compounds **3b-g** were prepared similarly.

3-Phthalimidomethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilides 4a : A mixture of compound **3a** (6.416 g, 0.02 mol), 4-aminoacetophenone (2.70 g, 0.02 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (2.2 g) in carbon tetrachloride (100 mL) was refluxed for 4 h

on a water bath under anhydrous condition. The solvent was distilled off and the solid thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, **4a**: yield 80%, m.p. 134 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3367 (N-H stretching), 3212 (C-H stretching), 1768 (C- acyclic), 1698 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1591 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1408 (C-N stretching in primary aromatic ring); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 2.2 (3H, s, -C- CH_3), 4.2 (2H, s, CH_2), 8.2 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–8.2 (11H, m, ArH); MS (m/z): 456 (M^+) (Found : C, 68.71; H, 4.23; N, 6.27. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$: C, 68.42; H, 4.42; N, 6.14%).

Compounds **4b-g** were prepared similarly.

Table 2. Some antimicrobial activity of the compounds prepared

Tested compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm) ^a		
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albican</i>
6a₁	18	16	16
6b₁	21	20	12
6c₁	21	18	12
6d₁	17	15	14
7a₁	18	19	14
7a₂	18	20	15
7a₃	16	16	10
DMSO	0	0	0
Ampicillin trihydrate	29	28	12
Cotrimoxazole	-	-	42

^aAverage of three readings.

3-(Phthalimidomethyl)-4-substituted cinnamoyl substituted benzanilides 5a₁: The suitable 3-phthalimidomethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilide **4a** (4.56 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (50 mL). To this solution was added a solution of salicylaldehyde (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 mL) followed by triethylamine (2 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 h. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was treated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and the product thus obtained was recrystallised from acetone : ethanol (1 : 1), **5a₁**: yield 62%, m.p. 161 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3360 (NH), 1675 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1594 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1410 (C-N stretching in primary aromatic ring), 762 (mono substituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 7.8 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, CH), 7.9 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, CH), 2.1 (3H, s, -C- CH_3), 4.4 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.6 (1H, OH), 8.3 (1H, s, NH), 6.6–8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (m/z): 560 (M^+) (Found : C, 70.78; H, 4.41; N, 5.1. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$: C, 70.71; H, 4.32; N, 5.00%).

Compounds **5a_{2-d}** were prepared similarly.

3-(Phthalimidomethyl)-4-(5-substituted isoxazoline) substituted benzanilides 6a₁: To a mixture of compounds

5a₁ (5.61 g, 0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.695 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) was added sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 mL) and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 8 h. After completion, the reaction mixture was cooled and the solid thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol : acetone (1 : 1), **6a₁**: yield 62%, m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3423 (OH), 3385 (NH), 3096 (CH), 1701 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1591 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1418 (C-N stretching in primary aromatic ring), 737 (mono substituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 1.8 (1H, d, J 6.7 Hz, CH), 2.1 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz, CH), 2.3 (3H, s, -C- CH_3), 4.4 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.6 (1H, s, OH), 8.8 (1H, s, NH), 6.6–8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (m/z): 575 (M^+) (Found : C, 68.92; H, 4.52; N, 7.4. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$: C, 68.86; H, 4.38; N, 7.3%).

Compounds **6a_{2-d}** were prepared similarly.

Table 3. Anthelmintic activity of the compounds prepared

Group	Compd.	Concn. (mg/mL)	Time taken for	Time taken for death ^a
			paralysis ^a (min)	(min)
1	6a₁	50	19	31
2	7a₁	50	16	33
3	6a₁	100	7	16
4	7a₁	100	9	12
5	Solvent control	-	-	-
6	Piperazine citrate	15	27	36

^aAverage of six readings.

3-(Phthalimidomethyl)-4-(5-substituted pyrazoline) substituted benzanilides 7a₁: To a mixture of compounds **5a₁** (5.61 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine dihydrochloride (1.05 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) was added anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 6 h. After completion, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and the solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid : acetone (1 : 1), **7a₁**: yield 57%, m.p. 197 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3365 (NH), 3307 (CH), 1710 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1682 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1434 (C-N stretching in primary aromatic ring), 742 (mono substituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 1.78 (1H, d, J 6.7 Hz, CH), 2.2 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz, CH), 2.4 (3H, s, -C- CH_3), 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.9 (1H, s, OH), 8.7 (1H, s, NH), 6.6–8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (m/z): 558 (M^+) (Found : C, 70.98; H, 4.59; N, 10.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 70.96; H, 4.69; N, 10.03%).

Compounds **7a₂-a₉**, were prepared similarly.

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